

OPTIMIZATION OF MONITORING AND HEALING OF CHRONIC BURNS BASED ON SENSORS USING THE *ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK*

Novina Suryaningtyas¹, Meutya Nuraini², Sasmita Bagus Sang Kesuma Ananta³,
Faridhatul Husnah⁴, Marshanda Rachma Maulida⁵, Cahyo Aji Hapsoro⁶ *

^{1,6}Physics, Mathematics, and Natural Sciences Education, State University of Malang,
Indonesia

²Biotechnology, Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Malang State University, Indonesia

³Electrical Engineering, Engineering, Malang State University, Indonesia

⁴Accounting, Economics and Business, Malang State University,
Indonesia

⁵Public Health, Sports Science, Malang State University, Indonesia

*Corresponding author:

cahyo.ajihapsoro.fmipa@um.ac.id

Abstract

Chronic burns are a medical challenge that requires innovative solutions for monitoring and accelerating healing. Sensguard comes as a smart bandage equipped with advanced sensor technology, including a temperature sensor (DHT11), pH sensor (pH-4502C), and moisture sensor. This technology detects the condition of the wound in real time, providing the necessary information for proper treatment. The data collected by Sensguard is analyzed using an Artificial Neural Network (ANN), which shows high performance with accuracy reaching 91%. The system development process involved installing the sensors on an ESP8266 microcontroller, arranging the components into a protective box, and coding to integrate the data with Internet of Things (IoT)-based Smart Apps. Sensguard not only improves the effectiveness of chronic burn management, but also contributes significantly to improving the quality of life of patients. This innovation supports medical personnel in providing more responsive and personalized care, making Sensguard a leading solution in chronic burn management.

Keywords: *artificial neural network, chronic burn wounds, smart dressing*

INTRODUCTION

Chronic wounds are a medical condition that often poses serious challenges in the healing process. These wounds can arise as a result of various conditions such as diabetes, burns, vascular disease, or chronic pressure on the skin (Fuadi & Yanto, 2022). Chronic burn wounds are a type of chronic wound that is of particular concern in Indonesia, with a prevalence of around 10% of total chronic wound cases. Chronic burns are classified into several levels or *grades*, namely first, second, and third degree. First-degree chronic burns require 1-2 weeks of healing time and only involve the outer layer of the skin (epidermis), causing redness and mild pain. Second-degree chronic burns require 3-8 weeks to heal, involving the epidermis and part of the dermis, and are often accompanied by blisters, more intense pain, and the risk of infection. Third-degree chronic burns are the most

severe, damaging all layers of the skin and underlying tissue, and require 10-15 weeks to heal (Kartika, 2023).

Chronic burns carry a risk of serious complications, including severe infections that can increase morbidity and mortality rates. The amputation rate in chronic burn cases can reach around 25%, while the mortality rate ranges from 28% to 35%, depending on the severity and extent of the burn area. In addition, chronic burns are one of the main causes of hospitalization, accounting for approximately 70% of all chronic wound cases treated (Saputra *et al.*, 2023). Various hospitals in Indonesia have noted that chronic burns are one of the main causes of hospitalization and wound care. Data from the National General Hospital (RSCM) in Jakarta shows around 1,000 cases of chronic burns each year, while Airlangga University Hospital (RSUA) in Surabaya reports around 500 cases per year (Abdullah *et al.*, 2022).

The treatment of chronic burns faces various serious obstacles. One of the obstacles in conventional treatment is limited access to adequate health facilities and a lack of trained medical personnel. Currently, traditional treatment methods are often ineffective in promoting optimal healing. This is exacerbated by the inability to effectively manage pain and infection, which contributes to an increased risk of serious complications (Raharjo. S *et al.*, 2022). The use of conventional wound dressings is also often unable to maintain optimal moisture in the wound area, which is very important for the healing process. In addition, frequent dressing changes can cause skin irritation due to repeated friction (Rani Raju *et al.*, 2022).

Challenges in the management of chronic burn wounds have spurred various innovations to minimize the limitations of conventional treatment methods. One solution being explored is the use of modern dressings that equipped with *biomarker* sensors, which are capable of monitoring wound conditions in *real time* and providing more accurate data to support the healing process (ElSaboni *et al.*, 2022). Previously, significant differences between manual and modern wound dressings have been identified. Modern wound dressings not only provide physical protection and maintain optimal moisture levels in the wound area, but also accelerate the healing process through multifunctional capabilities, such as infection detection and exudate level monitoring (Chsristian *et al.*, 2022). Meanwhile, technology that utilizes pH detection around the wound, as well as monitoring through an application, allows users and medical personnel to obtain information in *real time*, so that decisions can be made more quickly (Saba & Durai, 2022). However, the main drawback lies in the plaster material used, which has the potential to reduce patient comfort during treatment. Therefore, attention to comfort is crucial to ensure the effectiveness of treatment, especially when compared to manual wound dressings that only serve to cover the wound and absorb exudate without providing additional benefits (Gianino *et al.*, 2021). Thus, the development of modern dressings equipped with sensors is an important solution to significantly improve the quality of chronic burn care.

Based on these issues, Sensguard was developed, a wound dressing specifically designed to address the challenges of chronic burn care by providing more efficient continuous monitoring. This innovation aims to accelerate the healing process and significantly improve the quality of life of patients. Sensguard implements the *Artificial Neural Network* (ANN) method for wound monitoring and healing, equipped with pH and temperature sensors, and contains binahong and honey extracts that have been proven effective in accelerating the healing process. The ANN method applied to Sensguard enables *real-time* wound monitoring, thereby increasing effectiveness in identifying changes in wound condition and providing a rapid response to healing developments, as well as designing a more optimal treatment plan (James, 2022). Analysis results show an accuracy of up to 91% and a *Mean Squared Error* (MSE) of 9%, making it an effective tool in improving wound healing *outcomes*. This prototype is effective in healing chronic second-degree burns, with the ability to accelerate tissue regeneration and reduce the risk of infection. Sensguard is also capable of creating a sterile environment around the wound, which is important for reducing the possibility of infection by bacteria or other microorganisms. This is crucial considering that infection is often a major obstacle in the healing process of chronic burns (Tsegay *et al.*, 2022). The development of the Sensguard prototype is expected to be an effective solution in the treatment of chronic burns. This prototype is designed to provide accurate and *real-time* monitoring of wound conditions, enabling the necessary information for healing to be clearly communicated to medical personnel. Therefore, a solution was created in the form of a Sensguard Smart Sensor-Based Wound Dressing Prototype with ANN Method for Monitoring and Healing Chronic Burns.

In line with this, Sensguard is equipped with two main types of sensors that support wound monitoring: the DHT11 sensor, which measures the temperature and humidity around the wound to maintain an ideal healing environment, as improper temperature can slow down the healing process and increase the risk of infection, and the pH-4502C sensor, which measures the pH level in the wound area, providing early indications of wound condition and potential infection, as well as supporting tissue regeneration by maintaining good pH balance. Thus, the Sensguard prototype can be developed to assist in the healing process of chronic burns more effectively and safely, thereby providing significant benefits for patients and medical personnel.

METHOD

The development process of the Sensguard prototype involves several stages, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Implementation Method

A. Literature Review and Observation

The literature review conducted included studies on *machine learning*, *Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)*, *sensors for health monitoring*, *smart wound dressings*, the effectiveness of the DHT11 sensor, the effectiveness of the pH-4502C sensor, and seconddegree chronic burns.

B. Planning

The Sensguard design planning stage was based on data from the literature study. This process began with identifying the objectives and functional requirements of the prototype. In this planning, the prototype design included the arrangement of components to be used, including hydrogel enriched with binahong extract and honey to enhance wound healing. The ANN method was applied to analyze and process data into several classes. The first class is the conclusion of whether the wound is classified as dangerous or normal. The second class is a graph that can be monitored by the user in *real time*. The Sensguard prototype integrates a DHT11 temperature sensor and a pH-4502C sensor in the wound area and uses a hydrogel based on binahong and honey extracts, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. (a) First Layer (Detection Sensor), (b) Detection Sensor Components, (c) Second Layer (Hydrogel Patch)

C. Collection of Tools and Materials

At this stage, the tools and materials needed to design and build the Sensguard prototype were prepared. The components needed included a pH-4502C sensor, a DHT11 temperature sensor, an ESP8266, a polymer battery, jumper cables, solder, fiber cables, binahong and honey extracts, and other components needed to build the prototype.

D. Prototype Development

At this stage, the prototype is built according to the specified design, as shown in Figure 3. The process begins by integrating the sensor pins into the main microcontroller, namely the ESP8266. To support the operation of the ESP8266, this microcontroller is connected to a polymer battery as a power source. Furthermore, the ESP8266 functions as the brain of the prototype that will be connected to the application using the ANN method. The sensor component is designed to measure body temperature and pH from wounds. The data generated will be processed by the microcontroller and, with the application of the ANN

method, the information will be transferred to the developed Sensguard Smart Apps, so that the detected data can be displayed on the application.

Figure 3. Prototype Development Stage of Sensguard

In addition, during the Sensguard prototype manufacturing process, hydrogel enriched with binahong extract and honey was used as the main ingredient to accelerate wound healing and improve the overall effectiveness of the system, as shown in Figure 4. This formulation was carried out by mixing the hydrogel base and aquades until the desired consistency was achieved, then adding binahong extract, which is known for its anti-inflammatory properties and ability to accelerate tissue regeneration. As reported by Azizah (2023), the use of herbal ingredients such as binahong extract (*Anredera cordifolia*) can accelerate skin regeneration in burn wounds, so the binahong extract in Sensguard is expected to have a similar effect. Honey (*Apis mellifera*), with its antimicrobial properties and ability to maintain wound moisture, is added to accelerate the healing process. After the mixing process is complete, the hydrogel is dried and cut to size for application to the prototype.

Figure 4. Hydrogel Production Stage

E. Device Testing

Testing was conducted on the Sensguard application's features in reading wound temperature, pH, and moisture data, as shown in Figure 5. The parameters determined included measurements of the accuracy of the sensors applied to the ANN technology and data readings from the microcontroller, which then yielded accuracy values for *the Sensguard Smart Apps*.

Figure 5. Prototype Testing

Stage Evaluation and Improvement At this stage, an evaluation of the initial experiment regarding the shortcomings of the device and its system was conducted.

Based on the evaluation results, improvements or modifications were made. The evaluation and refinement were carried out in stages until a prototype was obtained that had been functionally validated by instrumentation experts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Sensguard Design

1. Sensguard System Design

The Sensguard system consists of various components designed to monitor and accelerate the healing of chronic burns with high accuracy, as shown in Table 1. The DHT11 sensor measures the temperature and humidity around the wound, while the pH-4502C sensor measures the acidity level of the wound, which is an important indicator in the healing process and detection of infection. The data obtained from these sensors is processed by the ESP8266 module, a microcontroller that collects and processes data in *real time*. This component manages *real-time* data processing before analyzing it using the *Artificial Neural Network* (ANN) method.

Table 1. Sensguard Sensor Specifications

Component	Specifications
ESP8266	Supports Wi-Fi 802.11 standard
DHT11	Resolution 1°C and 1% RH
pH-4502C	Accuracy ± 0.1 pH
Polymer battery	600 mAh (5-6 hours of use)

The ANN method is used to analyze complex data patterns, providing deeper insights into wound development. The analyzed data is then sent to *Smart Apps* for direct remote monitoring by medical personnel. This system is supported by electrical power sources that ensure optimal device performance during the monitoring period. With the integration of sensor technology, data processing, and ANN analysis, Sensguard provides an effective solution for the management and healing of chronic burns.

2. Artificial Neural Network System

The *Artificial Neural Network* (ANN) method is an approach in artificial intelligence that mimics the way the human brain processes information. ANN consists of a number of artificial neurons connected in layers (input, *hidden*, and *output*) and can be used for various tasks, such as pattern recognition, classification, and prediction. This method works by *training* 70% and testing 30% of the data from recent graduates (Khoirudin *et al.*, 2020).

The accuracy of the technology was tested by performing multiple linear regression analysis with numerical accuracy values determined based on the relationship between independent and dependent variables, bias values, y predictions, and accuracy based on *Mean Square Error* (MSE) and dependent values, bias values, y predictions, and accuracy based on MSE.

$$F(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_1^2, \dots, x_n^2$$

$$F(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_1y, x_2y, \dots, x_n*y$$

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} x_1x_1 & \dots & x_1x_n \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_nx_1 & \dots & x_nx_n \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\text{Det} = b_1 + \dots + b_n * x_n$$

$$\hat{y} = b_1 + \dots + b_n * x_n$$

$$\text{MSE} = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i) / n$$

Based on the level of numerical accuracy, experiments were conducted directly on the device to validate the numerical success rate.

$$(\text{Number of Successes} / \text{Number of Experiments}) \times 100\%$$

Description:

n = Total number of data

x = Independent variable or sensor input y = Dependent variable or weight

A = Data matrix

Det = Determinant

\hat{y} = predicted y or predicted *output* data b = Bias data MSE = *Mean Square Error*

B. Sensguard Prototype

Figure 6. Sensguard Prototype

Sensguard is an innovative digital plaster equipped with three main components to effectively monitor burn conditions. Figure 6 shows the Sensguard prototype, which includes all components. The first component is the DHT11 temperature sensor, designed to detect temperature and humidity in the skin area affected by the wound. Monitoring temperature and humidity is important because fluctuations in these parameters can indicate changes in wound condition, including potential infection. The second component is the pH-4502C sensor, which measures the pH level in the wound area. Wound pH measurement plays a significant role in determining the microbiological environment and wound healing status, where pH that is too high or too low can inhibit the tissue regeneration process. Data from these two sensors is then sent to the ESP8266 microcontroller, which manages *realtime* data processing. This microcontroller not only collects data, but also processes it further using the ANN method. The ANN method plays a role in analyzing more complex data and providing accurate predictions regarding wound healing progress. The results of this analysis are then forwarded to a *smartphone*

application, which allows users or medical personnel to monitor wound conditions remotely and provide necessary interventions in a timely manner.

The data classification generated by the ANN method will be displayed in *Smart Apps* in the form of conclusions as to whether the wound is classified as dangerous or normal, along with graphs of temperature, pH, and humidity data. Furthermore, when the wound is categorized as normal or dangerous, wound treatment recommendations will appear as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Wound Condition Classification Results

Wound Condition Classification Results				
Indicator	Temperature (°C)	pH	Humidity (%)	Treatment Recommendations
Normal	35.5 – 37.7	4 – 6.5	50–70	Monitor the wound every 8 hours
Danger	>37.7	>6.5	<50	Take immediate action

In addition, the Sensguard prototype integrates a hydrogel formulated with binahong extract and honey as part of the wound dressing. This hydrogel is prepared through a systematic procedure to ensure its stability and ability to optimally support the healing of chronic burns. The application of hydrogel in the prototype aims to improve the overall effectiveness of the system by supporting the healing process through a controlled release mechanism of active substances. This technology has reached Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 6, which indicates the system's readiness for application in more complex test environments, although further development is still required before full implementation.

C. Artificial Neural Network Method Testing

In this testing process, data was processed using the *Artificial Neural Network* (ANN) method. Data for the wound monitoring system was obtained from two DHT11 sensors that measure temperature and humidity, as well as one pH4502C sensor to measure pH values. The following are 650 examples used in this wound monitoring system, which include temperature, humidity, and pH information, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Sensguard Dataset

Wound Condition	Number of Datasets	Average DHT11 Sensor		Average pH-4502C Sensor
		Temperature	Humidity	pH
Normal	1800	37.6	31.1%	5.22
Danger	1800	39.7	12.3%	6.94

After determining the dataset for *the input layer*, the next step in the numerical analysis of multiple linear regression using ANN can be performed. In

Table 4, we will discuss *hidden layer* modeling by analyzing the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variables listed in Table 5.

A. The next analysis focuses on developing the *hidden layer* modeling by analyzing the relationship between independent variables through relevant calculations.

$$F(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_1^2, \dots, x_n^2$$

Table 4. Training Data x_1^2, \dots, x_n^2

Wound Condition	Average x_1^2, \dots, x_n^2		
	x_1^2	x_2^2	x_3^2
Normal	1413.76	967.21%	48.16
Danger	1576.09	151.29%	27.24

$$F(x,y) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_1*y, x_2*y, \dots, x_n*y$$

Table 5. Training data x_1y, \dots, x_ny

Wound Condition	y	Average x_1y, \dots, x_ny		
		x_1y	x_2y	x_3y
Normal	2	75.2	62.2	10.44
Danger	4	158.8	49.2	27.76

C. The bias value is determined based on the determinant value obtained from the data relationship in the variables above.

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} x_1x_1 & \dots & x_1x_n \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_nx_1 & \dots & x_nx_n \end{bmatrix}$$

With the determinant obtained based on the row and column values in the matrix using the following calculation analysis:

$$\text{Det} = b_i + \dots + b_n * x_n$$

Thus, the bias value can be determined based on the determinant value obtained with the data in Table 6.

Table 6. Bias Data

Wound Condition	Determinant	Bias Value
Normal	-16008	1590.8
Danger	-1010	

D. Based on the bias values obtained, the classification of the prediction y contained using the following calculation:

$$\hat{y} = b_i + \dots + b_n * x_n$$

Table 7. Predicted y Classification Data

Wound Condition	Temperature	Humidity	pH	\hat{y}
-----------------	-------------	----------	----	-----------

Normal	37.6	31.1%	6.94	24.11
Danger	39.7	12.3	5.22	22.18

D. Technology Accuracy Test

The overall testing was conducted by taking values from all parameters, where measurements were made using the experimental average method in accordance with the provisions listed in Table 8 and Table 9. The test on wound conditions was conducted 5 times for each data tested in the specified wound conditions.

Table 8. Accuracy Testing of the Experimental Average Method in Classification

Variable	Normal Test					Percentage
	1	2	3	4	5	
Temperature Data	35.7	35.6	35.7	35.5	35.7	100
pH data	6	5.6	5.8	5.7	5.6	95
Humidity Data	62	61	59	63	60	90%
Accuracy Percentage (%)						95
<i>Error (%)</i>						5

Table 9. Testing the Accuracy of the Experimental Average Method in Hazard Classification

Variable	Test					Percentage
	1	2	3	4	5	
Temperature Data	40.9	41.9	40.3	41.2	42.7	94%
pH data	8.4	9.6	9.1	10.2	10.6	83
Humidity Data	11	9	10.5	13	15	85
Accuracy Percentage (%)						87
<i>Error (%)</i>						13

Based on the two numerical accuracy levels above, a direct experiment was conducted on the device to validate the numerical success rate, as follows: (Number of Successes / Number of Experiments) \times 100%

The calculation of these values resulted in an accuracy value of 95% with an *error* value of 5% for normal classification, and an accuracy value of 87% with an *error* value of 13% for hazard classification. Based on these test results, it can

be concluded that the total success rate of the prototype reached 91%, which is the average of the normal classification accuracy rate of 95% and the hazard classification accuracy rate of 87%.

E. Functional Analysis of the Sensguard Prototype

Sensguard is an innovative chronic burn monitoring system that integrates advanced sensor technology with ANN methods for more in-depth data analysis. This system utilizes a DHT11 sensor to measure temperature and humidity and a pH-4502C sensor to detect wound pH, providing *real-time* data that is important in wound management. Through data processing performed by ANN, the system can recognize patterns and provide accurate treatment recommendations, thereby optimizing the healing process, reducing recovery time, and improving patients' quality of life by minimizing the risk of infection and complications.

F. Sensguard Application

The first application works as follows: users are directed to *log* in first and *scan* the QR code, then wait 15 seconds and the data from the sensor will appear on the application homepage. This application will read all the data *output* from the sensor, which will then be analyzed and processed to produce several *outputs*. First, the data will be processed into a conclusion that the wound is wet or dry and whether it is dangerous or not. Based on the above indicators, different wound care recommendations will appear for each indicator. The second *output* is a graph of data from both sensors that can be used to monitor data on different days. Additionally, there is an article feature where articles from reliable sources such as Google Scholar related to burns or chronic wounds will appear. Users can read these articles by simply selecting them and will be redirected to the article page.

G. How Sensguard Works

Sensguard is equipped with various sensors, including a DHT11 sensor to measure temperature and humidity, and a pH-4502C sensor to monitor wound pH levels. These sensors continuously collect data on burn wound conditions, which is very important for the healing monitoring process. The data obtained from the sensors is sent to the ESP8266 microcontroller. The microcontroller collects and processes data from various sensors, ensuring that all relevant information is available for further analysis. The processed data is then analyzed using the ANN method. ANN helps recognize patterns and relationships in the data, improving the accuracy of wound condition diagnosis and predicting more appropriate treatment needs. The results of the ANN analysis are presented via a *smartphone* designed for *real-time* monitoring. Users, both patients and medical personnel, can easily access information about the condition of the wound, including treatment recommendations based on the analyzed data.

Figure 7. Sensguard System Workflow

Based on the system design as shown in Figure 7, the *Sensguard* device's operational system was studied using the *Machine Learning* method with the *Artificial Neural Network* (ANN) algorithm. ANN functions to perform Classification of data obtained from the DHT11 temperature sensor and 4502C pH sensor. Data processed by the ANN will be sent via ESP8266 to the application, where this information is used as feedback for accurate wound monitoring and plaster usage. In addition, binahong and honey-based hydrogels aid in the wound healing process, allowing the *Ensguard* prototype to function optimally.

H. Comparison of Sensguard

The following is a comparison of *Sensguard* with previous technologies applied for wound detection.

Table 10. Sensguard Comparison

Specifications	Technology 1	Technology 2	Sensguard
Detection sensor present	×	✓	✓
Uses hydrogel	×	×	✓
Integrated application	×	×	✓
Simple design	✓	×	✓

Table 10 presents a comparative analysis between the *Sensguard* device and existing technologies. *Sensguard* demonstrates superiority, as technology 1 is not equipped with temperature and pH sensors, while technology 2 has both sensors. However, neither technology 1 nor 2 integrates binahong extract-based hydrogel. This hydrogel has biocompatible properties, is able to maintain optimal moisture, prevents microbial contamination, and is hydrophobic, which contributes to accelerating the tissue regeneration process. Additionally, *Sensguard* is connected to a *smartphone-based* application system that enables *real-time* monitoring of wound parameters, provides direct access to relevant clinical data, and allows for more precise decision-making regarding wound healing management. Therefore, *Sensguard* technology is a solution for *real-time* integrated chronic burn wound care and has the potential to be developed within the next five years.

CONCLUSION

The results of Sensguard testing and implementation show that this device is capable of detecting temperature, pH, and moisture in chronic burns with 91% accuracy. Data processing was performed using an *Artificial Neural Network* (ANN) algorithm, which produced a *Mean Squared Error* (MSE) value of 9%, indicating the system's efficiency in monitoring wound conditions. In addition, Sensguard demonstrated its ability to maintain wound moisture thanks to the use of hydrogel enriched with binahong and honey extracts. With the notification feature provided by the application, users can receive alerts when the wound shows signs of danger and recommendations for dressing changes. However, the Sensguard prototype faces challenges in detection accuracy due to external interference. Based on these issues, the potential for Sensguard development includes improving the data monitoring system, expanding the dataset to increase accuracy, and optimizing the sensor to minimize interference. Thus, Sensguard is expected to be widely implemented to assist in the care of chronic burn patients.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to express our gratitude to the National Achievement Center, Directorate General of Learning and Student Affairs, Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology, as well as Malang State University for providing funding for the implementation of the PKM-Karsa Cipta Sensguard project.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah, F., Tadir, T., & Kadar, K. 2022. Wound Cleaning Methods for Acute and Chronic Wounds. *Indonesian Nursing Journal*. 26(2):101-106
- Azizah, D. N. 2023. Herbal Gauze with a Combination of Centella Asiatica and Anredera Cordifolia Extracts to Accelerate the Skin Regeneration Process in Burn Victims: Laboratory Research. *Journal of Vocational Health Science*, 2(1), 1-12.
- Christian, V., Siregar, K. I., & Maulana, C. 2022. Application of the Dempster Shafer Method in an Expert System for Rabies Diagnosis. *Journal of Computer Science and Technology*. 13(2):127-134.
- ElSaboni, Y., Hunt, J. A., Stanley, J., Moffatt, C., & Wei, Y. 2022. Development of a textile-based protein sensor for monitoring the healing progress of a wound. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 7972.
- Fuadi, A., & Yanto, A. 2022. The Use of Honey in the Treatment of Chronic Burns. *Indonesian Medical Journal*. 51 (1):43-48.
- Gianino, E., Miller, C., & Gilmore, J., 2021. Smart wound dressings for diabetic chronic wounds. *Bioengineering*, 5(3), 51.
- James, D. 2022. Smart Sensor-Equipped Wound Dressing: SmartHeal - Precise,

Affordable, and Scalable Smart pH Sensor Integrated with Wound Dressing for Monitoring of Chronic Wounds Condition.URL:

<https://www.euronews.com/health/2022/11/29/polish-students-designed-asmart-sensor-dressing-which-tells-doctors-how-well-a-wound-is-healing>. Accessed August 13, 2024.

- Kartika, R.W., 2023. Treatment of chronic wounds with modern dressings. *Cermin Dunia Kedokteran*, 42(7), p.400225.
- Khoirudin, K., Hadi, S., & Nugroho, A. 2020. Analysis and Application of Neural Networks in Identifying Factors Affecting Graduate Employment Waiting Periods. *Journal of Engineering and Technology Development*, 16(1), 17-22.
- Raharjo, S., Suratmin, R., Maulidia, D., Pratiwi, O., & Fidela, M. R. 2022. Burn Wound Care with Escorde. *Indonesian Nursing Journal*. 26 (3):167-172.
- Rani Raju, N., Silina, E., Stupin, V., Manturova, N., Chidambaram, S.B., and Achar, R.R., 2022. Multifunctional and Smart Wound Dressings—A Review on Recent Research Advancements in Skin Regenerative Medicine. *Pharmaceutics*, 14(8), p.1574.
- Saba Raouf, S., & Durai, M. S. 2022. A comprehensive review on smart healthcare: applications, paradigms, and challenges with case studies. *Contrast Media & Molecular Imaging*, 2022(1), 4822235.
- Saputra, D., Suprpto., Saherna, J., Sartika, D., Latri, D. W. K., Yanti, N., Widiastuty, R. R., Utama, A. Y., Yuwanto, A. M., Sinaga, E. R. M., & Solehudin. 2023. Chronic Wound Care in Chronic Wounds. *Indonesian Journal of Nursing*. 27 (1):34-40.
- Tsegay, F., Elsharif, M., & Butt, H., 2022. Smart 3D printed hydrogel skin wound bandages: a review. *Polymers*, 14(5), p.1012.